

THE IMPORTANCE OF CHOOSING METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation

Nowadays, English is being taught around the world as a second and foreign language. Each country has its own way and curriculum of teaching this language. Using technologies in teaching English in the classroom is very hotly debated topic. According to some people's opinion it is very beneficial way of teaching students and students will engage the lesson better by using technologies in the classroom. But others think that traditional way has more benefits in the classroom.

While teaching students teachers should focus on their young learners are: 1) digital native in using technologies; 2) there is not the best teaching method or approach in teaching one language in foreign countries; 3) technologies will develop visual learners' remembering skills in the classroom; 4) lessons will be more fruitful if teachers give assignments based on websites and online language games; 5) Digital tools are one of the best way of encouraging students to learn foreign languages (Woodrow, 2011).

According to context and students' needs, methods and tasks should be changed. Each lesson they are given vocabularies with definition and grammar is also taught during the main and support lesson. Since learning Foreign language is rather complicated for some students, they have both main and support lessons at learning center. As these students are very young, they are interested in digital technologies and they are very digital-native students in the classroom. Because of this reason, they are given tasks from textbooks and online contents including YouTube, TedTalk and etc. To do interactive activities they have all the possibilities such as projector, speakers, printer, micro phone. Woodrow (2011), claimed that it is very important to engage all the students in the classroom. Since many textbooks are used for a long time, their reading materials or tasks may not be interesting for many students. To fix this problem, teachers should use online games or tasks instead of using traditional textbooks. To engage students to the tasks very well, I always focus on content of the listening and reading. Sometimes reading passage. might not be suitable for some students. That is why I add some materials or remove some tasks. As foreign language classes do not take much time, many students may be passive learners of the language. That is why extra lessons will develop their potentials. Joining to extra lesson is optional but it will give them many opportunities to develop their weak points. Although each country has already developed its syllabus, some materials are not interesting enough and some of them needs to be updated. Meaning that some pictures and reading passages are not modern and not understandable for youngsters. In these situations, I always use new alternatives for these materials. They best option I think that is to use special and updated web-pages which has many modernized topic.

Many students, nowadays, are digital-native and if they are provided only paper-based tasks, they might be bored. That is why I have decided to use internet sources which help students to do some activities online. Second reason of why I have selected it as a source for my students is its grammar and vocabulary level is fully suitable for my students' level. If grammar and meaning is complicated, learners will not be able to understand the meaning of

the passage. The next reason is text is about English Speaking Country and its famous building. To learn about the countries culture which they are earning its language is very useful tool for students. They will engage the language by using these kinds of topics. Using these kinds of materials helps them to develop their ideas in speaking exams.

Since international exams` reading tasks require both comprehension and speed reading skills, many second and foreign language learners find reading questions rather difficult. In most cases, they cannot finish reading passage three. As a result, their overall reading score will be about B1 or B2. To fix this problem, I have selected reading task and by providing tasks I will proof my ideas.

In conclusion, not only teacher`s ability in teaching but also other important factors are very important in learning foreign languages. As many students are kinesthetic learners, digital tools will be the best tool for them to engage the lesson better

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